

Conference Abstract

On the distribution of *Helichrysum arenarium* (L.) Moench (Asreraceae) in Bulgaria

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Abstract

Helichrysum arenarium (L.) Moench is herbaceous perennial plant belonging to Asteraceae family. The plant is well known in phytotherapy for its potential in the treatment of gallbladder disease and is classified as endangered in a number of European countries. In Bulgaria it is a protected species according to the Biodiversity Act (Annex 4) and is in the List of Species of Medicinal Plants under special regimen of conservation and use. The data on the distribution of *H. arenarium* in the Bulgarian flora have not been updated for more than 20 years. The aim of this study is to determine the current distribution of *H. arenarium* in Bulgaria on the basis of reviewing the available herbarium specimens in the Bulgarian herbariums, literature data, and personal collections. As a result, the locations of the species on the territory of the country were described and mapped. In Bulgaria *H. arenarium* is represented with only a few populations located in a limited area in the northeastern part of the country, in a narrow strip between the towns of Shumen and Varna.

Keywords

distribution, *Helichrysum arenarium*, Bulgarian flora

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